

Crohn's Disease and Psoriasis: An Association or Complication? - Regarding a Clinical Case

Rita Aldeia da Silva^{1*}, Ana Isabel Moreira Ribeiro¹, Diana Rita Oliveira^{2,3}, Cátia Lia Abreu⁴, Olga Ferreira⁵, Filipa Neiva^{2,3}

¹Pediatrics Department, Unidade Local de Saúde de Braga, Braga, Portugal

²Pediatric Gastroenterology Unit, Pediatrics Department, Unidade Local de Saúde de Braga, Braga, Portugal

³Clinical Academic Center, 2CA-Braga, Unidade Local de Saúde de Braga, Braga, Portugal

⁴Gynecology and Obstetrics Department, Hospital Trofa Saúde Braga, Portugal

⁵Dermatology Department, Hospital Lusíadas Braga, Portugal

Citation: Rita Aldeia da Silva, Ana Isabel Moreira Ribeiro, Diana Rita Oliveira, Cátia Lia Abreu, Olga Ferreira, Filipa Neiva. Crohn's Disease and Psoriasis: An Association or Complication? - Regarding a Clinical Case. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2024;3(12):1-4.

Received Date: 26 December, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 28 December, 2024; **Published Date:** 30 December, 2024

***Corresponding author:** Rita Aldeia da Silva, Pediatrics Department, Unidade Local de Saúde de Braga, Braga, Portugal

Copyright: © Rita Aldeia da Silva, Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*(ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

An 11-year-old girl with Crohn's disease, in remission with Azathioprine and Infliximab, developed vulvar swelling after nine doses of Infliximab, initially suspected to be an enterovaginal fistula. Pelvic MRI excluded fistulizing disease, and a skin biopsy revealed psoriasiform dermatitis. Treatment with topical Econazole, Triamcinolone, and Calcitriol led to significant improvement, but without complete clinical resolution. The biological therapy was switched to adalimumab, described in the literature as a first-line option for the treatment of psoriatic lesions associated with inflammatory bowel disease.

Keywords: Crohn's Disease; Psoriasis; Infliximab; Vulvar Psoriasis

INTRODUCTION

Inflammatory Bowel Disease and psoriasis are chronic inflammatory disorders frequently associated with systemic comorbidities that often occur together, particularly in children and adolescents.^[1] Crohn's disease (CD) is frequently associated with extraintestinal manifestations, including dermatological conditions, contiguous or metastatic lesions.^[2] Psoriasis is a complex dermatosis, associated with an increased risk of intestinal comorbidities.^[3] Despite their autoimmune nature, the pathogenesis of both diseases remains incompletely understood.^[3]

Tumor necrosis factor (TNF) inhibitors are widely used to manage these conditions. Notably, in CD, these therapies can paradoxically induce psoriasiform eruptions, presenting a unique clinical challenge.^[4]

CASE DESCRIPTION

An eleven-year-old girl, diagnosed with CD at age nine (Paris Classification A1L3L4B1) achieved luminal remission with Azathioprine and Infliximab. After sixteen months of Infliximab, she developed vulvar swelling and erythema with mild tenderness upon palpation, without discharge or pruritus (Figure 1). Gastrointestinal symptoms were absent, and both serum inflammatory markers and fecal calprotectin were within normal ranges.

Figure 1: Vulvar region - Image before initiating treatment, showing erythema and swelling

Suspecting an enterovaginal fistula, a 10-day course of antibiotics (Amoxicillin/Clavulanate and Metronidazole) was initiated, leading to partial improvement of vulvar symptoms. However, symptoms recurred after discontinuation. Pelvic Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) revealed "probable right-sided vulvar Bartholin's gland inflammation" (Figure 2A), excluding fistulizing disease. An attempted drainage showed no fluid, and clinical observation was recommended. No correlation was found between lesion activity and Infliximab infusions.

Histopathological analysis of a skin biopsy revealed "psoriasiform dermatitis without evidence of granulomas" (Figure 2B), supporting a diagnosis of psoriasis. Treatment with topical Econazole, Triamcinolone, and Calcitriol led to significant improvement.

Figure 2: Complementary diagnostic tests - A: Pelvic MRI showing thickening and an area of edema centered on the vulva and the right labium majus, with a maximum extension of 22 mm, displaying poorly defined borders, suggestive of a localized inflammatory process; B: Histological analysis revealing psoriasiform dermatitis without evidence of granulomas.

Three months later, a psoriatic-like lesion appeared on the earlobe, accompanied by increased swelling and elevated fecal calprotectin levels. A repeat pelvic MRI showed a reduction in the previously observed densification; however, intestinal findings were consistent with inflammatory activity. In light of these developments, therapy was switched to Adalimumab. Approximately one year after the switch, the vulvar lesion increased in size again, although it remained painless. Multidisciplinary follow-up remains ongoing.

DISCUSSION

This case presented a diagnostic challenge due to the overlapping clinical features of vulvar CD, classical psoriasis, and paradoxical psoriasis (PP). Vulvar CD, though rare, is characterized by granulomatous inflammation and often progresses asynchronously with intestinal disease.^[2] Psoriasis, significantly associated with CD, may arise as a primary condition or as a paradoxical reaction to biologic therapy, manifesting as a new-onset adverse event following treatment.^[1]

Skin biopsy played a pivotal role in narrowing the differential diagnosis, effectively ruling out vulvar CD and supporting the diagnosis of psoriasis. Despite the higher estimated frequency of PP in patients treated with biologics,^[1] the successful resolution of lesions with topical therapy without discontinuing Infliximab, followed by a recurrence under a different biologic, supports the therapeutic approach adopted.

Studies are ongoing to better understand PP and identify disease-specific markers for this effect.^[4,5] These efforts aim to improve diagnostic accuracy and guide tailored therapeutic strategies. This case underscores the need for multidisciplinary follow-up and careful evaluation of dermatological symptoms in patients receiving biologics, ensuring accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

REFERENCES

1. Alinaghi F, Tekin HG, Burisch J, Wu JJ, Thyssen JP, Egeberg A. Global Prevalence and Bidirectional Association Between Psoriasis and Inflammatory Bowel Disease-A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. J Crohns Colitis. 2020;14(3):351-360.
2. Shields BE, Richardson C, Arkin L, Kornik R. Vulvar Crohn disease: Diagnostic challenges and approach to therapy. Int J Womens Dermatol. 2020;6(5):390-394.
3. Fu Y, Lee CH, Chi CC. Association of Psoriasis With Inflammatory Bowel Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. JAMA Dermatol. 2018;154(12):1417-1423.
4. Pollard B, Utterson EC, Samson CM, Coughlin CC. Immunosuppressant-associated eruptions in pediatric inflammatory bowel disease: A case-control study. Pediatr Dermatol. 2022;39(4):563-566.
5. Agostino Bucalo, Federica Rega, Arianna Zangrilli, Valentina Silvestri, Virginia Valentini, Giorgia Scafetta, et al. Paradoxical Psoriasis Induced by Anti-TNF α Treatment: Evaluation of Disease-Specific Clinical and Genetic Markers. Int J Mol Sci. 2020;21(21):7873.